

Training on the Making of Fried Shallots (*Allium ascalonicum* L.) Products in Sigi District to Implementing the Recovery Concept of Agriculture and Food Security Impacted

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ABSTRACT: The concept of community empowerment in the socio-cultural field is an effort to strengthen small people through improving, strengthening, and upholding values, ideas, and norms, and encouraging the realization of social organizations that are able to provide control over political and economic treatments that are far from morality. Service activities are carried out in several stages such as socialization, FGD, training, and designing fried shallot business innovation tools. Socialization of fried onion product processing is carried out by providing training and FGDs in the form of slicing onions, frying and packing shallots. Furthermore, 3 fried shallot business innovation tools were designed in the form of slicing machines, spinner machines and shallot frying machines. Training activities for village youth cadres run smoothly and in accordance with the expected target, namely increasing community awareness about the function and role of village youth cadres in terms of seeking community agricultural products, especially in processing shallots in packaging so that these expectations can be achieved well.

KEYWORDS: Agriculture, Food Security, Shallots, Training, Village Cadres

INTRODUCTION

Central Sulawesi has a lot of potential that can be developed into regional excellence which is expected to improve the community's economy. These superior products are possible to be developed further with the help of lecturers at Untad, through continuous community service activities (Jumiyati et al. 2023) ^[1]. Agriculture is the main economic sector in Sigi Regency, but several challenges have emerged in recent years (Adeyemo et al. 2023) ^[2]. Climate variability, extreme weather changes, and plant disease problems can hinder optimal shallot production. In addition, there is a need for diversification of agricultural products to increase farmers' income and food security at the household level (Raeisi et al. 2016) ^[3].

Fried shallots (*Allium ascalonicum* L.) have potential as an alternative agricultural product that can increase added value and local competitiveness (Wang et al. 2023) ^[4]. Fried shallots not only have high nutritional value, but also have a stable demand in the local market and may be an additional source of income for farmers (Paramitha et al. 2022) ^[5]. Despite the potential of fried shallots, farmers may not have sufficient knowledge and skills in processing this product. Training on fried shallot product manufacturing is expected to provide an in-depth understanding of the production process, good product quality, and effective marketing strategies (Ko et al. 2022) ^[6].

Through this activity, we can support the concept of "Recovery of Agriculture and Food Security Impacted" by increasing agricultural productivity and developing value-added products (Farahbaksh 2021) ^[7]. This training is not only about making fried shallots but also how to implement sustainable agricultural practices and support the recovery of the agricultural sector in this region (Chyau & Mau, 2001) ^[8]. This concept refers to efforts to restore the agricultural sector and improve food security in regions or communities affected by various factors or crises. Such crises may involve climate change, natural disasters, disease outbreaks, economic changes or other factors that disrupt food production and food security (Olagunju et al. 2022) ^[9].

It is important to actively involve farmers in the development and implementation of this training. By listening to their experiences and inputs, we can ensure that the training is appropriate to local needs and conditions, and has a sustainable positive impact. The development of the fried onion industry can have a positive impact on local economic empowerment. By improving farmers' skills in making fried shallot products, it is expected to create new job opportunities and increase income at the household level.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Shallots (*Allium ascalonicum* L.): Fresh shallots were sourced from local farmers in Sigi District. The selection criteria included size, freshness, and absence of any signs of spoilage or disease, Cooking Oil: High-quality vegetable oil was used for frying to ensure the shallots were crisp and had a long shelf life, Salt: Fine-grained salt was used to season the fried shallots, Equipment: Frying pans, stoves, strainers, and storage containers were utilized during the training.sentences.

This activity will be carried out in the form of adult training by lecturers and assisted by students who have been equipped with skills beforehand. This training activity is designed in such a way, and adapted to the level of education, understanding and characteristics of the training participants, with language that is easily understood by students, interesting, and using the principles of Adult Education (POD). The realization of activities that have been carried out in community service activities for Women's Groups in Sigi Regency consists of 7 activities consisting of:

- 1) Survey of the location of community service activities;
- 2) Socialization of the program to the group;
- 3) Activity material: Shallot Cultivation and Prospects for Shallot Plants;
- 4) Making banner designs and product labels for fried shallots and shallot paste;
- 5) Activity material: Installation of onion cutting/slicing tools, video playback of the use of multipurpose slicing tools, and tutorials on the use of multipurpose slicing tools;
- 6) Activity Materials: Role, benefits and types of packing tools and materials, and Demonstration of product packing;
- 7) Activity Materials: Practice of making fried shallots, product labeling, packing of fried shallot products, and handover of onion slicer to all group members.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Public Participation

The target of this service program involves 20 village youth cadres, all of whom live in Sigi Regency. The highest level of education of the cadres is senior high school (SMA). The education level of the group ranged from elementary school to senior high school and its equivalent (vocational high school), but the average was junior high school. The average attendance of participants in all program activities was 18 people (90%), indicating that the enthusiasm of village cadre members in this service activity was very high because this activity was felt to be very inspirational and motivated them to create a business

Program socialization, the implementing team went directly to the village head and related stakeholders and explained the purpose of the service program and the results to be achieved. The FGD was conducted at the village office to discuss the problems faced by shallot farmers and what the village cadres want to improve welfare levels and determine the date of each activity. When the service activity program took place, the enthusiasm of the participants and a very good response to each activity were seen, this can be seen from the number of participant attendance / very good participant participation rate, which was attended by an average of 17 - 20 participants (88.75% average) out of 20 people in total. Participants who could not attend were solely due to important activities that could not be abandoned which coincided with the schedule of program activities. The number of participants who attended each activity is described in Table 1.

Table 1. Onion processing training activities

No	Activity	Number of Participants	Percentage (%)
1	Survey the location of the place of service activities	20 person	100
2	Socialization of program activities to cadres	20 person	100
3	Activity Material: - Onion Cultivation - Prospects for Onion Crops	20 person	100
4	Designing banners and product labels fried shallots	Service team	100
5	Activity Materials: - Installation of onion cutting/slicing tools	18 person	85

	- Video playback of the use of a versatile slicer tool - Tutorial on the use of a multi-purpose slicer		
6	Activity Materials: - Role, benefits and types of tools and materials packing - Product packing demonstration	16 person	75
7	Activity Materials: - Practice of making fried shallots - Product labeling – Packaging (packing) fried shallot products - Handover of onion slicer to all members	19 person	90

Participant Ability Level

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The results of observations during this service program activity took place, showing very positive things about the behavior of participants towards all program activities. The most obvious thing was seen during the practice of making fried shallots, where each participant was finally very adept at using an onion slicer and competed to show the ideal sliced onion results (neither too thin nor too thick). This was also seen during labeling and packaging, where each participant took turns doing it and showed very adequate results, although at first they had to repeat several times to get good results. The results of the achievement of the ability level of all participants during the training activities began at the knowing, understanding, clever, and skillful stages (application level). This means that the implementation of this service program activity provides new knowledge in terms of science and technology of onion slicing equipment that provides results with very good quality (significant) in producing onions which greatly affects the results of the products produced compared to before using this tool. In this case the participants only used a knife to slice with very inadequate quality results.

Evaluation of Activities

FGD with village youth cadres, agreed on the development of fried shallot business as a business opportunity, seeing the potential of this shallot commodity raw material very much in this area. The evaluation results of this service activity program have provided new science and technology, namely a practical shallot slicer with excellent quality results. This has also provided knowledge and skills to the participants in producing quality fried shallots. In addition, tutorials and demonstrations of label making and product packing have complemented the activities to get very attractive product results and can increase their selling value because of the quality and beauty of their appearance.

This service program has succeeded in providing skills in making fried shallots, as well as making business labels and adequate packing and good marketing methods. The development of this business among housewives requires support for business climate development and capital from the local government. The spirit of developing this business among housewives needs to continue to be developed through coaching and mentoring/incubation as well as partnership development to further expand the market (Figure 1).

Increasing the income of this village youth cadre is the goal to be achieved in this service program. The science and technology that has been provided has been able to make these cadres become skilled in producing fried shallots with qualified quality. The problem faced is the quality of shallot raw materials, most of which are still small. This is due to the harvesting of onions too quickly and the use of cultivation technology that is still very simple. This is a serious obstacle in the effort to develop the business in a better direction. Therefore, government support, in this case agricultural extension workers, is expected to participate in guiding farmers both in terms of good cultivation and in terms of harvest time activities for this commodity. Obstacles in the provision of business capital, business partners and sustainable business development need to be a concern of the government as a decision maker.

Figure 1. Fried shallots products in Sigi District

CONCLUSION

Training activities for village youth cadres run smoothly and in accordance with the expected target, namely increasing community awareness about the function and role of village youth cadres in terms of seeking community agricultural products, especially in processing shallots in packaging so that these expectations can be achieved well.

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